

Betel vine: A green gold for sustainable economic upliftment in rural India

Bubai Bhakta¹, Uttam Bhakta¹, Soumya Ghanti², Bana B. Jana², Paritosh Ghanti², Yuta Tsunemitsu³, Yang Jun³, Shinzo Yamane⁴, Kouhei Ohnishi⁵, Jatindra N. Bhakta^{1,2,5}

¹ R. Institute of Rural Human Resource Development, Purba Medinipur 721453, West Bengal, India

² Centre for Environmental Protection and Human Resource Development (KSI), B-10/289, Kalyani - 741235, West Bengal, India

³ Life and Environmental Medical Science Cluster, ⁴ Natural Sciences Cluster, Research and Education, ⁵ Research Institute of Molecular Genetics, Faculty of Agriculture, Kochi University, B200, Monobe, Nankoku, Kochi - 783-8502, Japan

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Corresponding Author:

Jatindra N. Bhakta

E-mail: lsjnbhakta@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Betel vine has immense nutraceutical, medicinal and economic importance with significant opportunity in employment generation and upliftment of socioeconomic conditions of rural peoples in India and also in other Asian countries, nonetheless; it has been neglected and poorly studied in various important aspects of betel vine so far. There is lack of substantial literatures regarding the cultivation and management processes and cost-benefit perspectives of betel vine farming along with so many other vital aspects, systematic identification of cultivars and conservation, complete screening of useful active phyto-molecules and its beneficial implications, genetic and molecular characterizations, quality improvement, disease control, fertilizer and integrated farming, etc. The present study attempted to draw a picture on cultivation and management processes and cost-benefit perspectives of betel vine farming by directly collecting data from experienced farmers of an important betel vine producing district, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, India. Study demonstrated a concise but practical account of cultivation, management and cost-benefit analysis of betel vine as data obtained from farmers of the investigated area. It has been observed from investigation that though, cultivation is labourious, it has highly beneficial cash crop potential compared to other cash crops having significant prospect in employment generation and socioeconomic development. Moreover, advanced researches can simplify hard and labourious cultivation process, improve the leaf quality, conserve cultivar, control disease, develop eco-friendly integrated organic based betel vine farming, protect post harvest damage and improve leaf marketing process. However, due to having immeasurable merits and national and international demands, it can be recognized as “green gold” and “household bank” for uplifting the rural economy.

1. Introduction

Betel vine (*Piper betle* L.) is dioecious and asexually propagated shade loving plant (Das et al., 2016; Patra et al., 2011). It is evergreen and perennial creeper belongs to Piperaceae family and bears characteristic heart shaped leaves of about 4 to 7 inch long and 2 to 4 inch broad (Das et al., 2016). It has different local names in India, such as – Paan in Hindi or Assamese or Oriya or Bengali, Tambula and Nagavalli in Sanskrit, Nagbael in Marathi, Naagarbael in Gujarati, Vetrilai in Tamil, Tamalapaku/Nagballi in Telugu, Veeleyada yele in Kannada, Vettila in Malayalam. It is also called by different names in different countries, such as - Pelu in Thai, Pu in Laos, Tràu in Vietnam, etc. It is one of the

important nutraceutically and medicinally important cash crops having potential economic values. Many literatures and reports mentioned that Malaysia is the origin of betel vine and it is distributed in South and Southwest China afterwards. Presently, it is cultivated in different counties of world such as - India, Bangladesh, Nepal, Srilanka, Pakistan, Myanmar, Indonesia, Thailand, Vietnam, Laos, Kampuchea (Ranade et al., 2011). It has different cultivars or landraces for example - *Bangla*, *Kapoori*, *Meetha*, *Sanchii* and *Desawari* etc. (Patra et al., 2011). According to Lakshmi and Naidu (2010), there are about 125 to 150 cultivars of betel vine available in India. There are about 100 varieties of betel vine in the world, of which about 40 are found in India and

30 in West Bengal (Guha, 1997; Guha, 2006; Maity, 1989; Samanta, 1994).

Although, the leaf of betel vine is primarily used as mouth freshener, it has immense social and cultural, economic, nutritional and medicinal importance as well as a folk (Siddha and Ayurvedha) reputation in respect to each and every plethora of human life from the dawn of civilization. Recently, several studies revealed that it contains essential oil 1% to 3% which has medicinal, antiseptic, antimicrobial properties. The significant property of betel leaf is the presence of many active phyto-chemicals such as, eugenol, hydroxychavicol, Pinene, Safrole, etc. those are greatly responsible for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-apoptotic, anti-cancer and anti-microbial efficacy (Kumar et al., 2010; Rai et al., 2011; Pradhan et al., 2013; Dwivedi, et al., 2010). Due to these properties, it is used to control many communicable and non-communicable diseases like cold, cough, bronchial asthma, rheumatism, stomachalgia and used to treat other diseases like bad breath, boils and abscesses, conjunctivitis, constipation, swelling of gums, cuts and injuries (Gundala et al., 2014). It has also wide applications in the formulation of syrup, tonic, cosmetics, ointments, etc.

Therefore, leaves of betel vine have huge demand and are consumed by about 15 to 20 million people in India and 2 billion foreign consumers annually (Das et al., 2016). In international market, it also has significant demands and is able to earn substantial foreign remittance in different betel vine cultivated countries. In India, betel vine crop provides Rupees 6000 to 7000 million national incomes per year and at the same time leaves of about Rupees 30 to 40 million worth is exported to other countries (Das et al., 2016).

Cultivation started from long time back, nonetheless researches in various aspects of betel vine for example – cultivation strategies, systematic identification of cultivars and conservation, complete screening of useful active phyto-molecules and its beneficial implications, genetic and molecular characterizations, quality improvement, disease control, fertilizer and integrated farming, cost-benefit analysis, socioeconomic condition of farmers, etc. have not yet been carried out such way, therefore, no prospective development has been found so far in this respect.

Therefore, information all most all of the above concerns is insufficient and lacking. Although, the cultivation strategies and cost-benefit analysis of betel vine varies with various factors such as - location, season, material and labour cost, market demands, etc., this paper has attempted to present a brief picture on current cultivation strategies and to draw a cost-benefit scenario of betel vine.

2. Methods

Study was conducted in Purba Mediniur districts (Latitude 21.8°N and Longitude 87.8°E; Area 4,785 km², population 4417377), West Bengal, India (Fig. 1). It is one of the higher and important betel vine growing districts in West Bengal, India (Bhattacharya et al., 2012) having about twenty betel leaf marketing centre (<http://purbamedinipur.gov.in/INDUS TRY-NEW.htm>). A vast area of this district is using for betel vine cultivation. Therefore, betel vine is one of the important resources of the investigated district. A substantial number of

families has employed and settled in betel vine cultivation. Most of the family has accepted betel vine cultivation as main source of income generation and some selected it as secondary source of income after paddy cultivation. There are several big markets for marketing betel vine.

Fig. 1 Location of Purba Medinipur district, West Bengal, India (symbol of betel vine within map of Indian depicting the major betel vine producing states)

To draw a picture on current cultivation strategies and a cost-benefit scenario of the betel vine cultivation, following information were procured from the well established and long experienced farmers of above present study site:

- i) Farm construction and cultivation of betel vine: construction materials, soil preparation, plantation, management, application of fertilizers and disease and pest controlling hazardous chemicals, etc.
- ii) Costs of construction and management (running expenditure) and total income per year for 0.4 ha area of cultivation.

Data was meticulously and precisely collected and processed for cost-benefit analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Farm construction

The betel vine farming of present studied site is close cultivation strategies. A strong farm shade (structure) is constructed for cultivation of betel vine. It is called as betel vine yard or widely known as “Boroj” or “Boreja” in West Bengal, India (Fig. 2). This boroj helps to create an artificial environment favourable for proper growth and protecting the vines from the adverse environmental conditions, such as, high temperature, sunlight, heavy cold, storm, heavy wind, and heavy rain.

Fig. 2 Photograph showing the boroj or yard of betel vine (closed cultivation)

Usually, the boroj is three dimensional rectangular or square in shape formed by fence (boundary wall) and roof and shade (Fig. 2). To construct the fence and roof of boroj, farmers generally use various kinds of materials, such as - bamboo pole, iron wire, coconut thread and plant's leaves. The main frame is generally formed by the bamboo pole. Recently, some farmers are using iron pipe or cement concrete pole for making side wall fence for durability purposes. Coconut thread and iron wire are commonly used as binding materials. Different specific plant's leaves such as coconut, date, palm, banana, etc. leaves are used as shade on the roof of the garden (Boroj) (Fig. 2). Now-a-days, shade nets produced from polyethylene are used to cover the roof of boroj (Fig. 3). Paddy straw or polythene sheet are also some time used by many farmers. Besides, a special kind of plants is cultivated in large scale which has huge market in this region to use as shade material.

It is surprising that most of the ingredients used in construction the boroj is natural bio-resource. These materials are biodegradable having no negative environmental impacts. Therefore, it can be recognized as eco-friendly farming in respect to boroj construction. Support stick is also cultivated by some farmers to use as support materials to climb up the betel plant. Some kinds of thread like grass (organic binder) are also use for binding betel plant with the support stick.

3.2. Soil sterilization and bed preparation

The nature of soils of the investigated area varies from clay to sandy. The soil of betel vine's bed is tilted one or two times and allowed for sunlight for few days before providing the roofs shade in order to sterilize soil bed. After sterilization, the large particles of soil are broken into small particles as the cutting of betel vine is easily planted and its root can easily grow without any inhibition. Recently, farmers are habituated to use the some kinds of pesticides, insecticides, fungicides, etc. for sterilizing the soil. After 2 or 3 weeks, about 1.0 to 1.5 ft width x 0.6 ft height bed is prepared allowing 1.0 ft space by making furrow of about 1.0 to 1.5 ft width x 0.6 ft depth between two beds. This space is used for walking for management of betel vine, such as - for watering, fertilization, spraying disease controlling agents.

From this information, it can be recommended that (i) farmers should oil cakes, cow or poultry dung, rotten farmyard manure (FYM) and leaves are thoroughly mixed or incorporated well with the topsoil by tilting with the help of

plough or power tailor to improve the fertility of soil; (ii) soil should be tilted several times (about 4 – 5 times) and allowed for sunlight for few days before providing the roofs shade, which help to reduce adverse effect of pathogens; (iii) farmers should avoid the hazardous chemicals in treating the soil.

Fig. 3 Original photograph representing the roof of boroj is made by shade net (closed cultivation)

3.3. Cultivation and management of betel vine

Betel vine is usually planted towards end of rainy season or end of winter seasons to obtain maximum survival in the investigated area. Bangla, Kappori and Sanchi types of cultivars are generally cultivated by the farmers of this area. It is real fact that farmers have no such concept about the quality cultivars. Farmers prefer cutting with two leaves (two nodes) for plantation. Sometimes cutting with one leaf (one node) or with more than ten leaves (more than ten nodes) are found to cultivate. The cutting is planted at about 2 to 3 inches below the surface and nodes are filled with top soil in bed maintaining 0.5 to 1.5 ft gap between two cuttings. After plantation, cutting is covered by the paddy straw to maintain the moisture condition of soil and inhibit to dry the leaf of betel vine. Prior covering, paddy straw is merged in water before one day to absorb water and make it soft in order to avoid any damage of leaf may caused during covering process. After cultivation a regular management process, watering and cleaning of grass grown in and around bed is continues. No sterilization of cutting followed by the farmers in planting process.

Fig. 4 Original photograph showing skill peoples are engaged in lowering the betel vine within farm

As betel vine is vegetatively propagated plant, special care should be taken for disease free planting process. The creeper cuttings are planted after proper dressing of bed and cutting. Before planting, cuttings can be treated by immersing in a fungicide mixture (1% bordeaux mixture or 0.1% ceresin and streptocycline 500 ppm) for about 15 to 20 minutes.

After about 4 to 6 weeks, the plant is grown; paddy straw is removed from bed and placed on the walking space to decompose in order to serve as fertilizer. A dead support stick is placed near each growing plant, which helps to betel vine for upright climbing at about 4 to 6 weeks for proper growth. The betel vine plant is irrigated at regular interval using the water pump. Except rainy season, irrigation is essential in winter and summer months. The farm is irrigated at every 8 to 10 in rainy season or 3 to 5 intervals in winter and summer seasons.

Most of the farmers commonly apply chemical fertilizers, such as, urea for nitrogen and Diammonium phosphate (DAP) for phosphorus at almost every 3 or 4 months interval at the rate of 400 to 600 kg/ha urea and 200 to 300 Kg/ha phosphorus. Some of the farmers are applying the organic fertilizer, mustard oil and ground nut oil cakes instead of chemical fertilizer. Application of cow dung, poultry manure and farm yard manure are rare or almost was not found. From the observation, the farmers are using huge chemical fertilizers without considering any soil quality. It is harmful to soil texture and quality. The farmer is unaware about the integrated organic betel vine farming. According to Chandra and Sagar (2004), Thomas et al. (2010, 2013) nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (NPK) fertilizer can be apply in the ratio of 160:80:40 Kg/ha. The organic, inorganic and mixed of both organic and inorganic fertilizers can be applied in the cultivation of betel crop (Thomas et al., 2010; 2013; Mandal et al., 1994). Farmers need to aware about the negative impact of chemical fertilizer and benefit of organic fertilizer. Chandra and Sagar (2004), Thomas et al. (2010, 2013) proposed that used of farm yard manure (FYM), cow dung, goat manure, poultry manure, oil cakes (neem, mustard, groundnut, coconut etc.), fish mill, rice bran, vermicompost etc. are beneficial in betel vine farming. The lowering of vine is done when the vines reach to (a height of about 1.80 – 2.10 m) roof shade (Fig. 4). Lowering process is commonly

performed 3 to 4 time/yr followed by soiling process (Fig. 4). Sometimes paddy straw is covered instead of soil (Fig. 5). Disease infection sometimes may cause great devastation and farmers suffer from huge damage and loss (Fig. 6). Various inorganic pesticides, insecticides, fungicides instead of chemical agents are applied to control the diseases (Fig. 7). In this respect, it can be mentioned that both inorganic fertilizer and pest or disease controlling agents have tremendous impacts on human and environmental health. Therefore, farmers should use the organic or bio-based fertilizer, pesticides, insecticides and fungicides instead of chemical agents to avoid the human and environmental hazardous problem.

Fig. 5 Lowered stem of betel vine is covered by paddy straw instead of soil

Fig. 6 Disease infected betel leaf of cultivated farm

Although harvesting of leaf is depends on market demands, it is usually done at 15, 30 or 30 days according to farmers need of the investigated area. Most of the cases, media man contracts to buy leaves from farmers. Media man collects leaf from farmers at very low cost compared to the actual market value. Therefore, farmers are usually suffered by such kind of practice. Besides, farmers are facing a

problem of post-harvest damages (Fig. 8). Cold storage facilities can provide a remedy to avoid this problem of damage. Farmers can store leave in cold storage and sale in market in the period of high market price to get more benefit. In such case, local administration should take initiative to control this type of malpractice by standardizing the rate and establishing the stable and organized betel vine market with cold storage facilities in different places of cultivating area of the country. Such, farmers will get the actual benefit of their hard labour which will also help to improve the socioeconomic condition of farmers.

Fig. 7 Pest and disease controlling hazardous inorganic agents (pesticides, insecticides, fungicides, etc.)

3.4. Cost-benefit

Costs of construction and management (running expenditure) and total income per year for 0.04 ha (i.e., 10 decimal) area of cultivation are represented in the following table (Table 1) on the basis of data collected meticulously from the farmers of investigated area. The cost-benefit analysis is largely depended on the contemporaneous market price of all concerned components, such as, construction materials, cutting of betel vine, fertilizers, chemicals required for controlling the diseases, irrigation facilities, labours, betel leaves, etc. However, the following cost-benefit analysis is calculated on the basis of market price of above components for the current year (2016) (Table 1).

From the above analysis, it can be observed that farmers can get a substantial benefit within two or three years after subtracting the establishment cost. Therefore, it is apparent that betel vine is a suitable cash crop for farmers, despite high input requirement. Other analysis for the years 2000 and 2010 also designated it as a profitable cash crop (<http://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/too-costly-to-grow-33173>). A big problem of this farming is the high labour crisis and cost and high rate of fertilizer cost, which significantly influence on the benefit of betel vine cultivation. That's why the above estimated cost and benefit is frequently fluctuated. However, farmer can set up a betel vine garden

only on a small about three decimal land area. From practical experience and also from investigation of some scientist, it has been established that a farm of 10 to 15 decimals can provide considerably good net profit for a family of five persons during the period from 10 to 30 years. Therefore, the betel vine farm is recognized as "household bank". Since, it can provide cash to farmer at every 15 days interval.

Fig. 8 The damaged betel leaf of post harvest

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated that a vivid practical concept of intensive betel vine cultivation followed currently in the investigated area and drawn a clear picture of current cost and benefit analysis. From above information, it can be recommended that awareness of farmers regarding the benefit of organic fertilizer application as well as adverse impact of chemical fertilizer including other chemical agents used in controlling the disease and pests is necessary to control environmental pollution especially soil pollution and develop sustainable cultivation of betel vine. Substantial research is needed in respect to modernize and simplify the present labourious betel vine cultivation process and improve quality. Although, the cultivation is labourious, it is highly beneficial cash crop compared to other cash crops. Local administration should take some initiatives for the market standardization and cold storage facilities to get actual benefit from this cultivation. Its significant multipurpose importance increases the national and international market demand. Additionally, it has high potential to generate employment. Due to having these merits of betel vine, it can be recognized as "green gold". Summarily, it can be concluded that the betel vine is a beneficial cash crop acting as a "household bank" for rural peoples having potential in uplifting the rural economy.

Table 1 Cost-benefit analysis of betel vine cultivation in 0.04 ha (i.e., 10 decimal) area (All calculations done according to information collected from skilled and expert farmers in Purba Medinipur district, West Bengal, India)

Items (10 decimal or 0.04 ha)	Year 2016	
	Cost in Rupees	Cost in US \$ (@ 1 US \$ = Rs. 66)
A. Cost of setting up a betel garden		
Soil for land elevation (2 ft high from ground to prevent submergence)	5000	75.75
Bamboo and other grass/straw for the outside structure	30000	454.54
Organic fertilizers	3000	45.45
Chemical fertilizers and Pesticides	3000	45.45
Stem cuttings of betel vine for plant propagation	10000	151.51
Stick on which the plant climbs	7000	106.06
Pump set for water supply from nearby sources	20000	303.03
Labour costs	40000	606.06
Total cost	118000	1787.87
B. Running and maintenance cost		
Climbing sticks replacement	8000	121.21
Fertilizer, pesticides, fungicides and hormones, etc.	7000	106.06
Repairing outside structure	8000	121.21
Labour costs every	30000	454.54
Diesel cost for pump	3000	45.45
Total cost	56000	848.48
C. Average annual income		
1 st year		
First harvest in 3 months	15000 – 20000	227.27 – 303.03
Subsequently every 2 weeks @ Rs. 3500 – 5500		
For 9 months (9 x 2 x 3500) and (9 x 2 x 5500)	63000 – 99000	954.54 – 1500
Total income	78000 – 119000	1181.81 – 1803.03
Subsequent years		
every 2 weeks @ Rs. 3500 – 5500		
(12 months), (12 x 2 x 3500) and (12 x 2 x 5500)	84000 – 132000	53.03 – 83.33
Total income	84000 – 132000	1272.72 – 2000
1st 2 years total expenditure = Rs. 118000 (establishment cost) + (56000 x 2 year's running cost) = Rs. 230000		
1st 2 years total income = Rs. (78000 + 84000) to (119000 + 132000) = Rs. 162000 to 252000		

References

- Lakshmi SB, Naidu KC (2010) Comparative Morphoanatomy of *Piper betle* L. cultivars in India. *Annals of Biological Research* 1(2):128–134
- Das S, Parida R, Sandeep IS, Nayak S, Mohanty S (2016) Biotechnological intervention in betelvine (*Piper betle* L.): A review on recent advances and future prospects. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine* 1–9, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apjtm.2016.07.029>
- Ranade SA, Soni A, Kumar N (2011) SPAR profiles for the assessment of genetic diversity between male and female landraces of the dioecious betelvine plant (*Piper betle* L.). In: Grillo O (ed.), *Ecosystems Biodiversity*, pp. 443–464
- Gundala SR, Yang C, Mukkavilli R, Paranjpe R, Brahmabhatt, M, Pannu V, et al. (2014) Hydroxychavicol, a betel leaf component, inhibits prostate cancer through ROS-driven DNA damage and apoptosis. *Toxicol Appl Pharm* 280(1):86–96
- Guha P (1997) Paan Theke Kutir Silpa Sambhabana” (In Bengali). In: Krishi, Khadya-O- Gramin Bikash Mela, Agricultural and Food Engineering Department, IIT, Kharagpur, India, pp. 15–19 [Guha, P. (1997). Exploring Betel Leaves for Cottage Industry. In: Festival on Agriculture, food, and development of village, Agricultural and Food Engineering Department, IIT, Kharagpur, India, pp. 15–19]
- Guha P (2006) Betel leaf: the neglected green gold of India. *Journal of Human Ecology* 19(2):87–93
- Maity S (1989) Extension Bulletin: The Betelvine. All India Coordinated Research Project on Betelvine, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hessarghatta, Bangalore, India
- Samanta C (1994) Paan chaser samasyabali-o-samadhan: Ekti samikkha (In Bengali) [A Report on the Problems and Solutions of Betel Vine Cultivation. In: Adhikari, H. R., Salt Lake City, Kolkata, India] (<http://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/too-costly-to-grow-33173>)
- Bhattacharya R, Mondal B, Ray SK, Khatua DC (2012) A study on bacterial disease of betelvine in West Bengal, India. *International Journal of Bio-resource and Stress Management* 3(2):211–216
- <http://purbamedinipur.gov.in/INDUSTRY-NEW.htm>
- Patra AP, Mukherjee AK, Acharya L (2011) Comparative study of RAPD and ISSR markers to Assess the genetic diversity of Betel vine (*Piper betle* L.) in orissa, India. *Am J of Biochem Mol Biol* 1(2):200–211
- Chandra G, Sagar RL (2004) Harvesting green gold: Cultivation of betelvine in Sundarban. *Indian Farmers Digest* 37(3): 5–13
- Thomas UC, Chandini S, Thomas A (2013) Integrated Nutrient Management Studies in betelvine (*Piper betel* L.). *International Journal of Applied Research and Studies* 2(7)
- Thomas UC, Chandini S, Anil Kumar S, Thomas A, Satyanarayana T (2010) Evaluation of Different Nutrient Management Options for Leaf Yield, Quality, and Economics of Betel Vine Cultivation. *Better Crops – South Asia* 16–17 ([http://www.ipni.net/publication/bca.nsf/0/B553675FA4561866852579A4007A4B4B/\\$FILE/B CSA%202010%20pg%2016-17.pdf](http://www.ipni.net/publication/bca.nsf/0/B553675FA4561866852579A4007A4B4B/$FILE/B CSA%202010%20pg%2016-17.pdf))
- Mandal BK, Choudhuri SK, Sengupta K, Dasgupta B (1994) Response of betelvine varieties to organic manure and prilled urea. *Indian J. Agric. Sci.* 64:297–301
- Rai MP, Karadka Ramdas K, Palatty PL, Rao P, Rao S, Bhat HP, Baliga MS (2011) *Piper Betel* Linn (Betel Vine), the Malignant Southeast Asian Medicinal Plant Possesses Cancer Preventive Effects: Time to Reconsider the Wronged Opinion. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention* 12:2149–2156
- Kumar N, Misra P, Dube A, Bhattacharya S, Dikshit M, Ranade S (2010) *Piper betle* Linn. a malignant Pan-Asiatic plant with an array of pharmacological activities and prospects for drug discovery. *Current science* 99(7):922–932
- Pradhan D, Suri KA, Pradhan DK, Biswasroy P (2013) Golden Heart of the Nature: *Piper betle* L. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry* 1:147–167
- Dwivedi BK, Kumar S, Nayak C, Mehta BK (2010) Gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GCMS) analysis of the hexane and benzene extracts of the *Piper betle* (leaf stalk) (Family: Piperaceae) from India. *J Med Plants Res* 4(21):2252–2255